

Tabla 1. Categorical Table

CATEGORIAL TABLE				
GENERAL PURPOSE	SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES	CATEGORY	SUBCATEGORY	AUTHOR (S)
Analyze the importance of social capital as a factor of competitiveness and economic growth in associations of the agro-industrial sector in the southwestern subregion of Norte de Santander	Identify the relationships between the associations and the agro-industrial sector that allow the competitiveness of the southwestern subregion of Norte de Santander	COMPETITIVENESS	PRODUCT INNOVATION	Manual de Oslo Comisión económica para América Latina y el Caribe
			MARKET INNOVATION	
			ORGANIZATIONAL INNOVATION	
	Know existing norms and values in the agro-industrial sector and the associations that produce vegetables and fruits to strengthen them in their productive base	SOCIAL CAPITAL	TRUST	John Durston
			COOPERATION	
			RECIPROCITY	
	Verify the development of the communities of the southwestern subregion of Norte de Santander in relation to the associations of the agro-industrial sector	ETHNODDEVELOPMENT	GENERATIONAL RELIEF	Arturo Escobar
			EMPOWERMENT	